

Next Generation Composites: Pushing the Boundaries of Performance and Sustainability

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Acknowledgment

Challenges

Performance

- Quality control

- Cycle time and throughput

- Process control
- Materials variability
- Data gaps
- \$\$
- Workforce Development

Sustainability

- \$\$
- Process
- End of Life (EoL) strategies
- Design for X
 - X: Disassembly
 - Recyclability
 - Carbon footprint
- Workforce Development
- Policy

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- **Workforce Development**

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 - X: **Disassembly**
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 - Carbon footprint**
- **Workforce Development**
- Policy

Emerging technologies that can push the boundaries

- **Advanced Materials**
- **Smart Resins**
- **Sustainable Processing Technologies**
 - Reduce or use “waste”
 - Reduce energy use
 - Enable recyclability
 - Lightweighting

Advanced Materials: CF

N. America composites market: \$ 20.3 B in 2022 to 31.9B in 2030*
Projected global market for CF \$4.7B in 2019 to 13.3 in 2029

A car body can weigh 75% less if made from CF composites instead of steel (7% increase in fuel economy for 10% reduction in vehicle mass)

Structural materials	Tensile Strength (GPa)	Density (g/cm ³)
Steel	2	7.8
CF (IM7)	5.6	1.78

Specific strength: [CF/steel]= 12.3
Specific modulus: [HS CF/steel] = 6
Specific modulus [HM CF/steel] = 16.7

50% composites

BMW i3 12% composite

Next Generation of CF Manufacturing @ low cost & energy

	Current Manufacturing of CF	Towards C2C manufacturing of CF
Energy input	high	> 80% reduction (Joule heating)
Feedstock (precursor)	Pan; 100% from fossil fuel	50% PAN and 50% lignin (renewable)
Cost	high	Low (Joule heating & low cost precursor)
Applications	Aerospace and high performance no-cost driven	Aerospace, automotive, structural (enabled by low cost)
Carbon footprint	low	Even lower (renewable precursor & less energy)
EoL strategies	Mainly landfill	Reclaim of CF due to use of sacrificial sizing

Next Generation of CF: where are we now?

CF	Diameter (μm)	Strength (GPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Elong @ break (%)	Ref.
PAN					
	11.0 ± 0.7	1.60 ± 0.3	223 ± 4	0.70 ± 0.1	S. Kumar
PAN/Lignin* (70/30)					
	11.0 ± 1.1	1.72 ± 0.2	230 ± 7	0.80 ± 0.1	S. Kumar
PAN/Lignin/CNT* (70/30/3)					
	9.5 ± 0.3	1.40 ± 0.2	200 ± 7	0.71 ± 0.1	S. Kumar
T300 (PAN)	~ 7	3.53	230	1.5	Toray
DOE target	-	1.72	172	-	DOE

Design for X

Smart Resins: Covalent adaptable networks

Epoxy based adhesives with associate/dissociate upon demand

The material transitions from a hard solid to a soft gel-like structure that can be dissolved away and reclaimed

Furfuryl alcohol is a renewable material derived from furfural, produced from hydrolysed biomass waste

Diels-Alder (DA) Reversible Chemistry

Diels Alder reaction is a [4+2] cycloaddition between a conjugated diene and an alkene, also called dienophile, in a cyclic fashion to form a 6-members ring structure

Otto Diels (1876–1954)
Nobel Prize 1950

Kurt A. Alder (1901–1958)
Nobel Prize 1950

Synthesis

Step 1: Prepolymer Synthesis

Monomers

Prepolymer

Step 2: Polymer Synthesis (crosslinking)

Diels Alder Crosslinkers

Dynamic Epoxy Networks

Performance: Tensile Properties

Performance: Self-healing

5 cycles of breaking (heating) and forming (cooling) the crosslinks (DA bonds)

Formation of the broken bonds (healing of the crack) upon heating

Performance: Reversible adhesion (sacrificial sizing)

Loctite and GEX-313 are commercially available bio-adhesives

EoL Strategy: Low cost CF composites using post-industrial waste

CF Prepreg waste (scrap/out of spec) from aerospace industry

- In-house waste management or transportation hazard
- Toxic chemical leach out to soil/ground water
- Virgin high-end performance materials end up in landfill
- \$1.5-\$6 /kg for disposal of scrap/out of spec CF prepreg
- Available at various shapes, forms and usually unknown thermal history

Convert out of spec CF preregs into high value products

Challenges

- Unknown quality, type, form
- Availability does not meet demand
- Need to use scalable industry-relevant manufacturing

Convert out of spec CF preregs into high value products

short out-time
SMC

Compression
→
molding

long out-time
No SMC

Tensile properties of CF composites made using CF out-of specs prepregs and SMC technology

Sustainable Technologies: Lightweight SMC composites

Add CNC on the GF surface

Add CNC in the resin

Coating of GF with CNC: Interfacial Shear Strength

60% increase

CNC as GF coating vs CNC as resin filler

Properties	0.17 CNC-30GF/ epoxy	30GF/1CNC-epoxy
Tensile modulus	10%	25%
Tensile strength	10%	30%
Tensile strain at break	14%	22%
Flexural modulus	40%	44%
Flexural strength	42%	33%
Flexural strain at break	10%	No change
Glass transition temp.	No change	No change

Lightweighting approach

Goal: Determine the CNC and GF content of a GF/CNC-epoxy composite so that it has the same specific modulus with 35 wt% GF/epoxy composites

Discontinuous randomly distributed fiber/composite

$$E_{Composite} = \frac{3}{8}E_{11} + \frac{5}{8}E_{22}$$

$$E_{11} = E_m \left(1 + 2 \frac{l_f}{d_f} \eta_L v_f \right) / (1 - \eta_L v_f)$$

$$E_{22} = E_m (1 + 2\eta_L v_f) / (1 - \eta_L v_f)$$

$$\eta_L = \left(\frac{E_f}{E_m} - 1 \right) / \left(\frac{E_f}{E_m} + 2 \frac{l_f}{d_f} \right)$$

$$\eta_T = \left(\frac{E_f}{E_m} - 1 \right) / \left(\frac{E_f}{E_m} + 2 \right)$$

Density:
$$\rho_c = \frac{1}{(w_f / \rho_f) + (w_m / \rho_m)}$$

Sample	E_c (GPa)	ρ_c (g/cm ³)	$E_{c, \text{specific}}$
25GF/epoxy	6.3	1.37	4.6
25GF/1CNC-epoxy	7.4	1.37	5.4
25GF/1.5CNC-epoxy	7.8	1.37	5.7
35GF/epoxy	8.0	1.46	5.5

Lighter Composites with addition of CNC: Practice

**Reduction of GF by 30%
(from 35 wt% to 25 wt%)**

Density decrease by 8.5%

Sustainable Technologies: Repurpose

Network University Members:

- Georgia Tech
- City University of New York
- University College Cork
- Queens University Belfast
- Munster Technological University

Funding (~\$2m 2014-current)

- NSF (CBET, PFI, I-CORPS)
- NYSERDA
- SFI
- DfE
- ENEL Green Power

Current Project Partners:

- Logisticus Group
- ENEL Green Power
- Siemens-Gamesa RE
- Cork County Council
- NYC Dept of Design and Construction (DDC)
- NREL Wind Manufacturing

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www.re-wind.info²⁴

Wind Turbine Blades to Bridges

BladeBridge is a concept to convert an entire wind blade or a large portion into the main load-bearing elements for a pedestrian bridge.

BladeBridge installed in Cork, Ireland, 2022

Wind Turbine Blades to Poles

Phase 1 Testing

Full-scale testing of braced line post assemblies for gravity and wind loads.

Phase 2 Installation at Smoky Hills, Kansas

Corner Pole Detail

Dead end Pole Detail

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Wind Turbine Blades to Noise Barrier & Feed Bunks

Noise Barrier - 6m high

Vertical full sections - N29 or V44 blades

Regular or irregular geometries

In this design multiple sections cut from blades are arranged in regular or irregular patterns to create the BladeBarrier. The image above shows large and small sections of a 21m V44 blade arranged in a repeating though irregular pattern to create a variegated wall.

Feed Bunks

37m GE blade

Variable length depending on local conditions.

The image above shows a feed bunk (or trough) cut from a section of the shell of 37m blade. The feed bunk shown above is 17m long making it easily transportable on a standard flatbed truck. The BladeBunk is lightweight and very durable and a potential replacement for heavy reinforced concrete existing feed bunks. The bunks can be designed in many different lengths with many different blade types. They can also be used as water troughs.

Workforce Development: Composite Engineers

- **Definition:** A special engineer that implements various composite components to build structures/products including design, materials selection, manufacturing, testing, optimization, certification, maintenance/repair
- **What does it take:** A BS in an engineering field, +2-3 years of industrial experience, + certifications, + PE license
- **Demand:** 92,000 jobs in US by 2027
- **Salary:** \$82-\$132K depending on skill level, experience and location (ZipRecruiter August 2023)

Composite Engineers: What's the challenge?

- It is not a widely taught subject
- There are no straight forward degrees on composites engineering
- Modeling and simulation tools like FEA are not taught in the context of composites
- Fast-pace changing field (i.e., new materials, processes etc, AI, VR)
- Fast growth of composites industry

Concluding remarks

Examples of how we can push the boundaries of performance and sustainability in composites

- Next generation CF- low cost, low energy input
- High performance CF composites using post-industrial waste
- Bio and reversible adhesive epoxies (sacrificial sizing, self-healing epoxies)
- Light SMC composites
- Repurpose GF wind turbine blades
- Workforce Development

